

LABOR MARKET INDICATORS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotatsiya This article analyzes the indicators of the labor market in Uzbekistan, as well as factors such as a favorable business environment for entrepreneurs, investment, tax policy, transparency, fairness of the judicial system.

Key words: labor market, unemployment, employment policy, private sector, agriculture, welfare level.

In order to ensure decent and formal employment of the population, the "Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the promotion of population employment in 2021-2030" was developed. The target indicators and indicators achieved as a result of the implementation of this strategy serve sustainable and comprehensive economic growth based on increasing effective and decent employment, national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030.

The basis of fundamental reforms launched in our country is the Strategy of Actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, and the issue of employment of the population occupies a special place in it. The sharp demographic situation in Uzbekistan, the rapid growth of the population and the entry of more than 500,000 young people into the labor market every year make the issue of stable employment of the population extremely urgent. Labor resources in Uzbekistan as of January 1, 2021 are 19.1 million. people, the economically active population is 14.8 million. people, total employment 13.2 million. people, of which 5.7 million are in the official sector of the economy. people (43.3%), 5.6 million in the informal sector of the economy. people (42.8%), 1.6

million people in need of employment. people (10.5%) and those who went to work abroad - 1.8 million. organized a person.

In the past 5 years, digitization of most processes in the labor sector, adaptation of labor statistics to the standards of the International Labor Organization, provision of its real indicators, development and wide use of new forms of employment, transparency and all services to the population as much as possible convenient and quick implementation was achieved through electronic platforms.

The new version of the Law "On Employment of the Population" was adopted in 2020 and it became the Law with direct effect. It reflects the main principles of the state in the field of employment and is based on modern labor law norms. In particular, new means of regulating the labor market, in particular, encouraging entrepreneurship, self-employment, vocational training of the unemployed, improving their skills, taking into account the length of service, paying unemployment benefits, and placing them in work. agencies, citizens temporarily working outside the republic and other important issues were covered.

Also, the Labor Code was reworked based on the experience of advanced countries, and after various discussions, it is scheduled to be adopted in 2021. Modern methods of regulating labor relations, between the employer and the hired employee, social partnership, individual labor relations and other issues have been solved in it.

The Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations is moving from passive measures (payment of unemployment benefits) to active employment policy (especially for youth, women, persons with disabilities) and by providing vocational and entrepreneurship training, microcredits and subsidies to the unemployed. started a wide way to support his employment.

For the first time in our country, the problems of employment with informal labor and the hidden economy began to be openly discussed, and our state took extensive measures to reduce its scope. Informal employment of the population

exists even in the most developed countries, and it is not only negative, but also performs some important social and economic tasks.

Firstly, by ensuring that the human resources who could not find work in the formal sector of the economy get a job and, as a result, income, it reduces unemployment (a real means of social protection for the helpless), prevents poverty, and spends their income in the formal sector, increasing domestic demand and increasing GDP. will encourage.

Second, informality is often a stepping stone to the formal sector as a way to start a business.

Informal employment is a widespread phenomenon all over the world, and reducing its scope requires the state to carry out a systematic and comprehensive policy in this area. According to the report of the International Labor Organization, 6 out of 10 workers (61% of the employed) and 4 out of 5 enterprises in the world operate informally in the shadow economy. The formation of employment with informal labor is an economic activity that has economic, legal, social and cultural factors, and the ultimate goal of which is to obtain economic benefits, and in most cases it is a compulsory economic activity. New technologies allow to reduce the transaction costs of economic units, to formalize economic activity, reducing the human factor and its participation as much as possible, as electronic registration, integrated and automated service provision.

The digital economy requires the training of highly qualified personnel, the flexible, consistent and continuous development of professional skills and knowledge, and creates opportunities for registration and convenient formalization of the population's employment, in particular, labor relations using digital electronic platforms. The widespread penetration of the digital economy into the life of society requires the use of the Internet in labor activities in all areas to be in the conditions of an integral connection with the "real" and "virtual" world. The impact of the digitalization of the economy on the labor market in Uzbekistan can be seen in the

introduction of the "Unified National Labor System" interagency software-hardware complex in 2020. This electronic information system collects information about employees, individuals, and vacant jobs in offices and organizations.

Decreasing the level of informal employment as a component of the underground economy shows the direct connection with the reduction of the share of the underground economy and the need to solve it through effective comprehensive measures of the state.

Due to the fact that the high level of informal employment causes various risks for the stable socio-economic development of the country, the importance of including it in the criteria of the economic security system has been scientifically justified. Its high level leads to the country's development, social conflict, an environment of equal competition, inequality, increased stratification, incomplete inclusion of the population in the official social system, non-compliance with the legal order in society, financial losses and other socio-economic consequences. (Fig. 1).

(Figure 1). Labor market statistics of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022

Labor resources - 19,488.00 thousand

The average population is 35,642,000

In our country, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6098 dated October 30, 2020 "On organizational measures to reduce the underground economy and increase the efficiency of tax authorities", June 8, 2020 "Entrepreneurial activity and o "On measures to simplify state regulation of self-employment" No. PQ-4742 and August 11, 2020 "Attracting poor and unemployed citizens to entrepreneurship, increasing their labor activity and professional Decisions PQ-4804 on additional measures aimed at vocational training and ensuring employment of the population are aimed at reducing the level of the underground economy and informal employment.

These documents provide for the transparent operation of the underground economy and informal labor by creating an economically advantageous institutional environment and conditions within the framework of the law, not to eliminate it through administrative methods and prohibitions.

Thus, the transition to the digital economy model in the world economy is taking place along with radically new, qualitative changes in socio-economic relations both at the state level and at the level of business structures. Registration of economic units and formalization of informal employment serve to ensure decent and effective employment.

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